

An experimental immune activation regimen targeting a receptor activated in CNS metastasis, VSTM2L.

Pre-Clinical/Clinical/Translational/Phase1-3
Compassionate Use Document (FDA format)

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1. Metastasis to the brain occurs in a significant fraction of patients with breast cancer¹⁻³.
2. We mined published RNA-sequencing and microarray data^{4,5} to compare primary and metastatic tumor transcriptomes for the discovery of genes associated with brain metastasis in humans with metastatic breast cancer.
3. We found that V-set and transmembrane domain-containing 2-like, encoded by VSTM2L, was among the genes whose expression was most different in the brain metastases of patients with metastatic breast cancer as compared to primary tumors of the breast.
4. VSTM2L mRNA was present at increased quantities in brain metastatic tissues as compared to primary tumors of the breast.
5. We concluded that modulation of VSTM2L expression may be relevant to the biology by which tumor cells metastasize from the breast to the brain in humans with metastatic breast cancer.
6. The alarmingly high rate of central nervous system metastasis occurring in patients with solid tumors including cancer of the breast and lung¹⁻³ demands an enhanced understanding of the transcriptional makeup of brain metastatic tissues to support identification of therapeutic targets.
7. We performed a comparative transcriptome analysis of primary and metastatic tumors in patients with brain metastatic breast cancer using published RNA-sequencing data⁴.
8. We also utilized a separate, published microarray gene expression dataset⁵ to determine if target differential expression was a shared feature of CNS metastasis among patients with breast cancer.
9. We present our findings here together with data supporting approval of Compassionate Use Protocol complaint for the use of an investigational agent (under development) that targets VSTM2L.
10. We assume activation of the immune cell surface marker silences or significantly suppresses a local immune response that is specifically anti-tumor.
11. As such, we expect a monoclonal antibody targeting VSTM2L to activate endogenous anti-tumor defense. The magnitude of this activation is not yet understood.
12. High tumor expression of VSTM2L in humans is correlated more rapid metastasis to a distant organ site (Figure 1).
13. The complete regimen in its initial formulation also contains monoclonal antibodies that target
 - i. PD-1,
 - ii. PD-L1 and
 - iii. CTLA4 to maximize endogenous anti-tumor response.
14. The FDA Compassionate Use Protocol outlined here is for patients whose disease has progressed following treatment for CNS metastatic breast cancer.

Methods

We used datasets GSE191230⁴ and GSE10893⁵ for this global differential gene expression analysis of brain metastatic breast cancer in conjunction with GEO2R. GSE191230 was generated using HiSeq X Ten technology with $n=8$ primary breast tumors and $n=5$ brain metastases from patients with breast cancer; analysis was performed using platform GPL20795; all patients were HER2+. GSE10893 was generated using Agilent-011521 Human 1A Microarray G4110A technology with $n=4$ primary breast tumors and $n=11$ brain metastases from patients with breast cancer; analysis was performed using platform GPL885. The Benjamini and Hochberg method of p -value adjustment was used for ranking of differential expression but raw p -values were used to assess statistical significance of global differential expression. Log-transformation of data was auto-detected, and the NCBI generated category of platform annotation was used.

Results

We performed comparative transcriptome analysis of metastatic tumor tissues from patients with metastatic breast cancer using published RNA-sequencing and microarray data^{4,5} for rapid discovery, validation and translation of novel therapeutic targets.

VSTM2L is differentially expressed in the brain metastases of patients with brain metastatic breast cancer.

Through blind, systems-level analysis of published RNA-sequencing and microarray data⁴, we identified V-set and transmembrane domain-containing 2-like, encoded by VSTM2L, as a differentially expressed gene in the brain metastatic tissues of humans with breast cancer (Chart 1). When sorting each of the genes expressed in brain metastases based on significance of difference as compared to primary tumors of the breast, VSTM2L ranked 397 out of 21403 total transcripts (Chart 1), equating to 98.1% differential expression. Differential expression of VSTM2L in the brain metastases of patients with breast cancer was statistically significant (Chart 1; $p=2.91E-07$).

We interrogated a second microarray dataset⁵ for target validation, comparing global gene expression patterns between brain metastases and primary tumors of the breast, again revealing differential expression of VSTM2L in metastasis to the CNS in humans with breast cancer (Chart 2). When sorting each of the genes expressed in brain metastases as compared to primary tumors of the breast, VSTM2L ranked 327 out of 17418 total transcripts, equating to 98.1% differential expression (Chart 2). Differential expression of VSTM2L in the brain metastases of patients with brain metastatic breast cancer was statistically significant (Chart 2; $p=1.04E-03$).

Differential expression of VSTM2L in the brain metastases of women with metastatic breast cancer, both identified blindly and through whole transcriptome methodologies, suggested that differential expression of VSTM2L is a transcriptional feature of metastasis to the CNS, rather than an experimental artifact, a reflection of idiosyncratic behavior in cell culture or animal models, or an observation from a single laboratory.

VSTM2L is expressed at higher levels in the brain metastases of patients with metastatic breast cancer.

We referenced provided log fold-change data from whole transcriptome differential gene expression analysis (Chart 1) of primary tumors of the breast and brain metastases to determine direction of change in VSTM2L expression in brain metastatic tissues. VSTM2L was expressed at higher levels in the brain metastases of patients with breast cancer as compared to primary tumors of the breast (Chart 1).

Thus, by mining published RNA-sequencing and microarray data^{4,5} in an unbiased fashion, we identified V-set and transmembrane domain-containing 2-like, encoded by VSTM2L, as among the genes whose expression was most different, transcriptome-wide, in the brain metastases of patients with breast cancer; VSTM2L messenger RNA was present at higher quantities in metastasis to the brain.

Discussion

We provided evidence here that V-set and transmembrane domain-containing 2-like, encoded by VSTM2L, is among the genes whose expression is most different in the brain metastases of patients with brain metastatic breast cancer, and that VSTM2L mRNA is present at increased quantities in brain metastatic tissues as compared to primary tumors of the breast. Evaluation of the effects of genetic depletion of VSTM2L in mouse models of metastatic breast cancer on metastasis to the central nervous system is merited. Modulation of VSTM2L expression may be relevant to the processes by which breast cancer cells exit the breast, enter the vasculature and/or lymphatics, reside in the lymph nodes, evade immune clearance, breach the blood-brain barrier and colonize the brain.

References

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Figure 1: High tumor expression of VSTM2L is associated with significantly more rapid distant metastasis.

Legend: Distant-free metastasis survival (DMFS) in months based on expression of VSTM2L in the primary tumor of $n=2765$ humans with breast cancer, stratified into two populations: high or low expression of VSTM2L

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Rank: 397
p-value: 2.91E-07
stat: -5.1289298
log2FoldChange: -4.39458637
baseMean: 969.61
Gene: VSTM2L
Gene name: V-set and transmembrane domain-containing 2-like

Chart 1: VSTM2L is differentially expressed in brain metastatic breast cancer when comparing brain metastases to primary tumors of the breast.

The rank of global differential expression, the p -value with respect to differential expression transcriptome-wide, stat (the Wald statistic), fold change in gene expression expressed as log2, basemean, the average of normalized counts among all samples analyzed the gene and gene name are listed in this chart.

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Rank: 327
probe ID: 22064
p-value: 1.04E-03
t: -4.01
B: -0.630893
Gene: VSTM2L
Gene name: V-set and transmembrane domain-containing 2-like

Chart 2: VSTM2L is differentially expressed in brain metastatic breast cancer when comparing brain metastases to primary tumors of the breast.

The rank of global differential expression, probe/transcript ID, the *p*-value with respect to differential expression transcriptome-wide, *t*, a moderated *t*-statistic, *B*, the log-odds of differential expression between the groups compared, the gene and gene name are listed in this chart.